

GENETIC ASSESSMENT OF SELECTED KHARIF SORGHUM GERMLASM ACCESSIONS FOR GRAIN ZINC AND IRON CONTENT

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Abstract:

Over billions of years sorghum is one of the major millets and an important crop cultivated on a large scale worldwide. The rising issues of malnutrition are taken into consideration and studies are formulated to study the nutrient efficiency of the various genotypes. The overall study concluded that high zinc and iron content was recorded for the genotype AKSV-438 followed by AKSV-440 and AKSV-267 and all these three genotypes were found superior than the checks PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti. It was thus observed that, the genotypes which recorded high zinc content also recorded higher iron content. In respect to the morphological studies, minimum days to 50% flowering was observed in the genotype AKSV-267 and check Parbhani Shakti followed by AKSV-438, AKSV-440. Plant height was observed to be minimum in the check PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti among the genotypes the maximum plant height was observed by AKSV-438 followed by AKSV-440 and AKSV-267. The Panicle length was observed to be maximum for the genotypes AKSV-438 followed by check Parbhani Shakti, PVK-801 and genotype AKSV-267 however, minimum panicle length was recorded by genotype AKSV-440. Panicle width was observed to be nearly similar in all the genotypes and checks under study.

Key words: sorghum, zinc and iron, genotypes, Panicle width.

Introduction:

Sorghum is an important grain and fodder crop. It is the fifth most important cereal crop and one of the most important major millets grown in Africa, Asia and America. Popularly known as King of Millets it comprises of 25 species of flowering plants belonging to the Family of Poaceae (Graminae), (Price *et al.*, 2005) Genus: *Sorghum* and Species: *bicolor*, which is also one of the major staple crops cultivated in India. It is extensively cultivated in marginal rainfall areas of the tropics and subtropics. The wild species of sorghum represent a potential diverse source of germplasm for sorghum breeding programmes. Being a C4 plant it is photosynthetically efficient, drought tolerant and resistant to water-logging (Doggett, 1988), and grows in various soil conditions (Dillon, *et al.*, 2007). It is the second cheapest source of energy and micronutrients after pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) and a majority population in Africa and central India depend on sorghum for their dietary energy and micronutrient requirement (Parthasarathy *et al.*, 2006). The intake of food poor in nutritional quality, particularly lacking in crucial micronutrients, is one of the serious global health problem in the developing world. In rural households the intake of iron and zinc is lower than the recommended dietary allowance thus, biofortification i.e., the enhancement of bioavailable micronutrient concentrations in food crops through plant breeding is a cost effective and sustainable solution for tackling micronutrient deficiencies, particularly in the developing world.

Sorghum grain is rich in starch, protein, micronutrients and crude fiber but low in fat (Chavan and Patil 2010), making it a good staple. It is also rich in thiamin, riboflavin and niacin. It is gluten-free and a safe food for celiac patients or people with known gluten allergies. The slow digestibility of sorghum starch makes it a food option for diabetics (Wong *et al.*, 2009). Based on the WHO recommended nutrient intake (RNI) or U.S. recommended dietary allowance (RDA), sorghum is a good source of energy and eleven nutrients, of which nine are micronutrients that are critical to health and well-being. The bioavailability of Fe in sorghum is 5% and that of Zn is 20% depending upon the form in which sorghum is consumed (United Sorghum Checkoff Program, 2010). Biofortification of sorghum by increasing mineral micronutrients (especially iron and zinc) in the grains provides a sustainable solution to iron and zinc deficiency (Pfeiffer and McClafferty 2007). Sorghum cultivars differ in Fe and Zn content in grain.

Material and Methods:**Plant Material**

The experimental material consisted of three genotypes which were randomly selected for micronutrient analysis of Zinc and Iron based on their diversity for various traits along with two checks under study.

All these three genotypes along with two checks were sown on the field of Sorghum Research Unit, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. The genotype material utilized for the study are given below with their details-

- 1) **AKSV-440:** This line is developed in the biofortification program at Akola center. It has high zinc and iron content. It is developed by selection from (EC 488403).
- 2) **AKSV-438:** This line is developed in the biofortification program at Akola center. It has high zinc and iron content. It is developed by selection from (IC 286441).
- 3) **AKSV-267:** This line is developed in the biofortification program at Akola center. It has high zinc and iron content. It is developed by selection from (AKSV-267 selection 4).
- 4) **PVK-801:** This is an kharif sorghum variety released for cultivation by Vasantao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth (VNMKV), Maharashtra.
- 5) **Parbhani Shakti:** It is India's first biofortified sorghum variety with significantly higher iron and zinc content. It is developed by ICRISAT from the improved variety ICSR 14001 and was released for cultivation by Vasantao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth (VNMKV), Maharashtra.

Micronutrient estimation

Grains free from soil or metallic contamination were subjected to the estimation of contents of Fe and Zn following Atomic Absorbance Spectroscopy (AAS) based method. Dried grain sample was accurately weighed and determination of micronutrients in the sorghum grain sample was done by Di-Acid digestion method. It is carried using 10 ml, 9:4 mixture of HNO₃ : HClO₄ with 1.00 gm whole grain sample is placed in 100 ml volumetric flask. The flask is placed on low heat hot plate in a digestion chamber. Then, the flask is heated at higher temperature until the production of red fumes ceases. The contents are further evaporated until the volume is reduced to about 3 to 5 ml but not to dryness. The completion of digestion is confirmed when the liquid become colourless. After cooling the flask, add double distilled water and volume is made up to 50 ml. The solution is then filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The aliquots of this solution are used for the determination of Zinc (Zn) and Iron (Fe) with the help of Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS), (Jackson 1967). The measured concentrations of Fe and Zn were considered appropriate when they agreed well with the certified values.

Result:**Zinc and Iron content:**

During the year, 2018-19, (Table 1) the genotype AKSV-440 (30.24 ppm, 34.50 ppm) recorded highest zinc and iron content respectively, followed by AKSV-438 (27.70 ppm, 33.20 ppm) and AKSV-267

(22.07 ppm, 30.35ppm) and were found superior to the checks PVK-801 (13.01 ppm, 24.70 ppm) and Parbhani Shakti (16.76 ppm, 24.15 ppm). Similar trend of zinc and iron content was reported in the year 2019-20 where, genotype AKSV-440 recorded highest zinc and iron content (29.18 ppm, 33.29 ppm, respectively), followed by genotype AKSV-438 (26.73 ppm, 32.04 ppm) and genotype AKSV-267 (20.01 ppm, 22.92 ppm) and were also found a bit superior in comparison to the checks PVK-801 (12.55 ppm, 23.84 ppm) and Parbhani Shakti (16.17 ppm, 23.30 ppm). In the year 2020-21, the genotype AKSV-438 recorded highest zinc and iron content (45.01 ppm, 52.78 ppm, respectively) followed by genotype AKSV-440 (32.46 ppm, 41.38 ppm) and genotype AKSV-267 (22.44 ppm, 32.45 ppm), all these three genotypes recorded highest performance for zinc and iron content as compared to the checks PVK-801 (12.89 ppm, 24.48 ppm) and Parbhani Shakti (1.60 ppm, 23.93 ppm). Whereas, in the year 2021-22 the genotype which recorded highest zinc and iron content was AKSV-440 (27.24ppm, 32.89ppm) followed by AKSV-438 (23.02 ppm, 30.53 ppm) and AKSV-267 (22.07 ppm, 30.35 ppm) and was found to be superior than the checks PVK-801 (12.74 ppm, 24.57 ppm) and Parbhani Shakti (24.57 ppm, 24.80 ppm).

However, overall high zinc content was recorded for the genotype AKSV-438 (30.61 ppm) followed by AKSV-440 (29.78 ppm) and AKSV-237 (21.65 ppm) and all three genotypes were found to be superior to the checks PVK-801 (12.80 ppm) and Parbhani Shakti (16.77 ppm). For overall iron content was found to be highest in the genotype AKSV-438 (37.14 ppm) followed by genotype AKSV-440 (35.51 ppm) and AKSV-267 (29.02 ppm) and was found superior to the checks PVK-801 (24.40 ppm) and Parbhani Shakti (24.05 ppm).

Morphological Results:

The morphological studies of the three genotypes AKSV-440, AKSV-438 and AKSV-267 and two checks PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti was done during the four years i.e. 2018-19, 2019-20, 2020-21 and 2021-22.

During the year 2018-19, days to 50 % flowering was found lowest in the genotype AKSV-438 and AKSV-267 (71 days) followed by AKSV-440 (74 days) and were observed to be early flowering than the checks PVK 801 (89 days) and Parbhani Shakti (73 days). Minimum plant height was recorded by the checks PVK-801 (110 cm) and Parbhani Shakti (135 cm) as compared to the genotypes under study AKSV-267 (260 cm), AKSV-440 (285 cm) and AKSV-438 (290 cm). Maximum length of panicle was observed in the genotype AKSV-438 (24 cm) followed by AKSV-267(19 cm) and the checks PVK-801 (18 cm) and Parbhani Shakti (17 cm) and minimum panicle length was observed in the genotype AKSV-440 (11 cm). Panicle width was found to be similar in all the genotypes under study including checks (7 cm and were at par with each other). Grain yield per panicle was observed to be maximum in the genotype AKSV-267 (48.30 g) followed by AKSV-440 (42.67 g) and AKSV-438 (33.64 g) whereas the checks recorded a moderate grain yield as compared to the genotypes under study that is PVK-801 (24.73 g) and Parbhani Shakti (25.75 g). The 100 grain weight was recorded to be maximum in the checks PVK-801 (2.64 g) and Parbhani Shakti (2.54 g) whereas the genotypes such as AKSV-440 (2.03 g) recorded highest seed index (100 grain weight) followed by AKSV-267 (1.81 g) and AKSV-438 (1.78 g).

During the year 2019-20, minimum days to 50 % flowering was recorded by the check Parbhani Shakti (68 days) followed by the genotypes AKSV-267 (70 days), AKSV-440 (72 days) and AKSV-438 (74 days) and maximum days were recorded by the check PVK-801 (85 days). Plant height was recorded to be minimum by the checks PVK-801 (110 cm) and Parbhani Shakti (135 cm) followed by the other genotypes AKSV-267 (240 cm), AKSV-438 (275 cm) and AKSV-440 (280 cm). The panicle length was observed to be maximum in genotype AKSV-438 (23 cm) followed by check Parbhani Shakti (19 cm) and PVK-801 (17 cm) however, minimum panicle length was recorded in the genotype AKSV-267 (15 cm) and AKSV-440 (10 cm). The panicle width was observed to be nearly

similar for almost all the genotypes and checks under study. In respect to the yield, maximum grain yield per panicle was recorded by the genotype AKSV-267 (42.27 g) followed by AKSV-440 (40.26 g) and AKSV-438 (31.00 g) however, the checks recorded medium yield as compared to the genotypes under study PVK-801 (20.81 g) and Parbhani Shakti (25.98 g). The seed index was recorded maximum for the check PVK-801 (2.98 g) and Parbhani Shakti (2.37 g) however, the genotype which recorded moderate seed index were AKSV-440 (1.92 g) followed by AKSV-438 (1.74 g) and AKSV-267 (1.66 g).

The observations recorded in the year 2020-21 minimum days to flowering was recorded by the genotype AKSV-267 and check Parbhani Shakti (70 days) followed by AKSV-438 (72 days), AKSV-440 (74 days) and maximum days were recorded by the genotype PVK-801 (86 days). Minimum plant height was observed in the checks PVK-801 (105 cm) and Parbhani Shakti (145 cm) followed by the genotypes AKSV-267 (265 cm), AKSV-440 (270 cm) and AKSV-438 (280 cm). Maximum panicle length was observed in the genotype AKSV-438 (24 cm) followed by the check Parbhani Shakti (20 cm), genotype AKSV-267 and check PVK-801 (18 cm) and the minimum panicle length was recorded by the genotype AKSV-440 (11 cm). Panicle width was observed to be nearly similar for all the genotypes and checks under study. In regards to the grain yield per panicle, maximum grain yield was observed by the genotype AKSV-267 (45.43 g) followed by AKSV-440 (42.33 g) and AKSV-438 (32.33 g) on the other hand checks recorded medium yield PVK-801 (23.49 g) and Parbhani Shakti (28.90 g). The 100 grain weight recorded was observed to be highest in the checks Parbhani Shakti (2.35 g) and PVK-801 (2.33 g) whereas, the genotypes recorded seed index where maximum was recorded in the genotype AKSV-440 (1.96 g) followed by AKSV-267 (1.85 g) and AKSV-438 (1.75 g)

During the year 2021-22, the minimum days to 50 % flowering were recorded by the genotype AKSV-438, AKSV-267 and check Parbhani Shakti (72 days each) followed by AKSV-440 (75 days) and maximum days to flowering was recorded by the check PVK-801 (87 days). Plant height was observed to be minimum in the checks PVK-801 (108 cm) and Parbhani Shakti (135 cm) followed by genotypes AKSV-267 (250 cm), AKSV-438 (285 cm) and AKSV-440 (290 cm). Panicle length was observed to be maximum in AKSV-438 (22 cm) followed by AKSV-267 and checks PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti (18 cm each) and minimum length of panicle was recorded by genotype AKSV-440 (12 cm). Panicle width was observed to be similar in all the genotypes and checks under study. In respect to the grain yield per panicle, maximum grain yield was recorded by the genotype AKSV-267 (47.61 g) followed by AKSV-440 (44.98 g) and AKSV-438 (34.92 g) which was more as compared to the checks grain yield per panicle PVK-801 (23.96 g) and Parbhani Shakti (25.82 g). The seed index (100 grain weight) was observed to be maximum in the check Parbhani Shakti (2.65 g) followed by PVK-801 (2.48 g) however, among the genotypes under study AKSV-440 recorded maximum seed index (2.16 g) followed by AKSV-438 (1.80 g) and AKSV-267 (1.62 g).

However, from the overall study of the mean values recorded minimum days to flowering was observed in the genotype AKSV-267 and check Parbhani Shakti (70.75 days) followed by AKSV-438 (72.25 days), AKSV-440 (73.75 days) and maximum days was observed in PVK-801 (86.75 days). Plant height was observed to be minimum in the check PVK-801 (107.50 cm) and Parbhani Shakti (138.75 cm) among the genotypes the minimum plant height was observed by AKSV-267 (253.75 cm) followed by AKSV-440 (281.25 cm) and AKSV-438 (282.5 cm). The Panicle length was observed to be maximum for the genotypes AKSV-438 (23.33 cm) followed by check Parbhani Shakti (18.50 cm), PVK-801 (17.75 cm) and genotype AKSV-267 (17.50 cm) however, minimum panicle length was recorded by genotype AKSV-440 (11.08 cm). Panicle width was observed to be nearly similar in all the genotypes and checks under study.

Discussion:

During the study, in all the four years study, overall high zinc content was recorded for the genotype AKSV-438 followed by AKSV-440 and AKSV-237 and all three genotypes were found to be superior than the checks PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti. A similar trend was also observed for the iron content which was found to be highest in the genotype AKSV-438 followed by genotype AKSV-440 and AKSV-267 and were found superior to the checks PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti. It was thus observed that, the genotypes which recorded high zinc content also recorded higher iron content, it was in confirmation with the findings of Kumar et al., (2012) and Chavan et al., (2023) where they recorded positive association between grain iron and zinc content which enabled them to develop high yielding cultivars with different maturity backgrounds.

In respect to the morphological studies, minimum days to 50% flowering was observed in the genotype AKSV-267 and check Parbhani Shakti followed by AKSV-438, AKSV-440 and maximum days was observed in PVK-801. Plant height was observed to be minimum in the check PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti among the genotypes the minimum plant height was observed by AKSV-267 followed by AKSV-440 and AKSV-438. The Panicle length was observed to be maximum for the genotypes AKSV-438 followed by check Parbhani Shakti, PVK-801 and genotype AKSV-267 however, minimum panicle length was recorded by genotype AKSV-440. Panicle width was observed to be nearly similar in all the genotypes and checks under study. The genetic diversity in sorghum was also studied by Durrishahwar et al., (2012) and found variation for all the genotypes under study.

Table: 1. Summary of the Micronutrients and Morphological contributing traits (Dr. PDKV, Akola) during the year 2018- 19 to 2021-22

Phenological Traits	Years of Testing	No. of Locations	AKSV 440	AKSV 438	AKSV 267	Checks	
						PVK 801	Parbhani Shakti
Zinc (Zn) content (ppm)	2018-19	1	30.24	27.70	22.07	13.01	16.76
	2019-20	1	29.18	26.73	20.01	12.55	16.17
	2020-21	1	32.46	45.01	22.44	12.89	16.60
	2021-22	1	27.24	23.02	22.07	12.74	17.53
	Overall mean	4	29.78	30.61	21.65	12.80	16.77
Iron (Fe) content (ppm)	2018-19	1	34.50	33.20	30.35	24.70	24.15
	2019-20	1	33.29	32.04	22.92	23.84	23.30
	2020-21	1	41.38	52.78	32.45	24.48	23.93
	2021-22	1	32.89	30.53	30.35	24.57	24.80
	Overall mean	4	35.51	37.14	29.02	24.40	24.05
Days to 50% flowering	2018-19	1	74	71	71	89	73
	2019-20	1	72	74	70	85	68
	2020-21	1	74	72	70	86	70
	2021-22	1	75	72	72	87	72
	Overall mean	4	73.75	72.25	70.75	86.75	70.75
Plant height (cm)	2018-19	1	285	290	260	110	135
	2019-20	1	280	275	240	105	140
	2020-21	1	270	280	265	107	145
	2021-22	1	290	285	250	108	135
	Overall mean	4	281.25	282.50	253.75	107.50	138.75
Panical length (cm)	2018-19	1	11	24	19	18	17
	2019-20	1	10	23	15	17	19
	2020-21	1	11	24	18	18	20
	2021-22	1	12	22	18	18	18
	Overall mean	4	11.08	23.33	17.50	17.75	18.50
Panical width (cm)	2018-19	1	7	7	7	8	8
	2019-20	1	7	7	7	8	7
	2020-21	1	7	7	7	8	8
	2021-22	1	7	7	7	8	8
	Overall mean	4	7.00	7.00	7.00	8.00	7.75
Grain yield per panical (g)	2018-19	1	42.67	33.64	48.30	24.73	25.75
	2019-20	1	40.26	31.00	42.27	20.81	25.98
	2020-21	1	42.33	32.33	45.43	23.49	28.90
	2021-22	1	44.98	34.92	47.61	23.96	25.82
	Overall mean	4	42.56	32.97	45.90	23.25	26.61

100 grain weight (g)	2018-19	1	2.03	1.78	1.81	2.64	2.54
	2019-20	1	1.92	1.74	1.66	2.98	2.37
	2020-21	1	1.96	1.75	1.85	2.33	2.35
	2021-22	1	2.16	1.80	1.62	2.48	2.65
	Overall mean	4	2.02	1.77	1.74	2.61	2.48

Conclusion:

The overall study concluded that high zinc and iron content was recorded for the genotype AKSV-438 followed by AKSV-440 and AKSV-237 and all these three genotypes were found superior than the checks PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti. It was thus observed that, the genotypes which recorded high zinc content also recorded higher iron content. In respect to the morphological studies, minimum days to 50% flowering was observed in the genotype AKSV-267 and check Parbhani Shakti followed by AKSV-438, AKSV-440. Plant height was observed to be minimum in the check PVK-801 and Parbhani Shakti among the genotypes the maximum plant height was observed by AKSV-438 followed by AKSV-440 and AKSV-267. The Panicle length was observed to be maximum for the genotypes AKSV-438 followed by check Parbhani Shakti, PVK-801 and genotype AKSV-267 however, minimum panicle length was recorded by genotype AKSV-440. Panicle width was observed to be nearly similar in all the genotypes and checks under study.

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